

VALUE ADDITION IN TOMATO: A CASE STUDY ON NAGPUR ORANGE GROWERS ASSOCIATION

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Abstract

The study entitled "Value Addition in Tomato: A Case Study on Nagpur Orange Growers Association" evaluates the capital investment, cost structures, returns, and marketing strategies involved in a tomato processing unit. Focusing on the production of Tomato Ketchup, Tomato Sauce, and Tomato Puree, the research analyzes raw material consumption, processing efficiency, labor, packaging, and marketing costs to determine profitability. The unit processed 19356.40 kg of raw materials, with output distribution as follows: Tomato Ketchup (50.32 per cent), Tomato Sauce (35.48 per cent), and Tomato Puree (14.19 per cent). The cost structure consisted of fixed costs amounting to Rs. 53.52 lakhs and variable costs of Rs. 42.94 lakhs. Per-kilogram production costs were Rs. 155.25 for Tomato Ketchup, Rs. 156.01 for Tomato Sauce, and Rs. 140.24 for Tomato Puree, with packaging representing a significant portion of costs. Marketing expenses per kilogram varied between Rs. 12.50 for Tomato Ketchup, Rs. 13.25 for Tomato Sauce, and Rs. 20.38 for Tomato Puree. The unit generated gross returns of Rs. 148.18 lakhs, with Tomato Ketchup contributing 52.82 per cent, Tomato Sauce 37.25 per cent, and Tomato Puree 9.93 per cent. The net profit amounted to Rs. 42.12 lakhs, with input-to-output ratios of 1:1.45 for Tomato Ketchup, 1:1.44 for Tomato Sauce, and 1:1.07 for Tomato Puree. Notable value additions were observed, with Tomato Puree showing a 782.87 per cent increase, followed by Tomato Ketchup and Tomato Sauce with 682.61 per cent. The study concludes that tomato processing is economically viable, though challenges such as securing initial capital, skilled labor shortages, and climate control, as well as transportation and storage issues, need to be addressed for further optimization.

Keywords – Tomato, analyzes, optimization..

Introduction

The concept of "value-added," which emerged in the 1920s, refers to enhancing a product's value through processes like food preservation, a practice dating back to ancient civilizations such as Mesopotamia and Egypt, who used techniques like drying, smoking, and salting. Over time, methods like pasteurization, developed by Louis Pasteur in the 1860s, further advanced food safety by eliminating harmful microbes in products like milk and juice without compromising quality. Today, agriculture and food processing remain crucial to India's economy, contributing 6 per cent to the nation's GDP. India is the second-largest tomato producer globally, with major states like Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka driving production. The country's food processing sector, particularly in fruits and vegetables, is rapidly expanding, with the processed tomato products market growing over 30 per cent annually (USDA Report, 2024). Products such as tomato paste, ketchup, and sauces dominate this space, with brands like MAGGI and KISSAN leading a ₹1,000 crore market that grows at 20 per cent per year (Times of India). This surge in demand, alongside new market entrants, signals immense opportunities for growth in the sector.

This study emphasized the crucial role of value addition in the food processing industry. First, transforming raw agricultural products into processed goods significantly increases their market value, resulting in higher profits for both farmers and businesses. Additionally, processing techniques such as canning, freezing, and drying extend the shelf life of food products, thereby reducing waste and ensuring food availability over longer periods. This value addition often includes fortifying foods with essential nutrients, which enhances the nutritional quality of the products and contributes to public health. Moreover, the value addition process creates numerous job opportunities in processing, packaging, and distribution, thereby boosting employment in both rural and urban areas. Processed foods also cater to diverse consumer preferences, opening new markets and increasing demand for a variety of products. Lastly, by providing a reliable market for processed goods, value addition helps stabilize farmers' incomes and encourages sustainable agricultural practices, ultimately benefiting the economy as a whole.

Company Profile

1.	Establishment Year	:	1960
2.	Name Under	:	Central Hindustan Orange and Cold Storage (CHOCS)
3.	Taken Over	:	Maharashtra Agro-Industries Development Corporation Limited (MAIDC)
4.	Year of Taken	:	1972
5.	Nomenclature	:	Nagpur Orange Growers Association (NOGA)
6.	Business Type	:	Government owned
7.	Company Status	:	Active
8.	Location	:	Plot No. B-17 to B-20 MIDC industrial area, Hingna, Nagpur- 440016.
9.	Products	:	Jams, Marmalade, Ketchup, Sauce, Puree, Squashes, Syrups, Juices, Pickles etc.

Objectives of study

To study capital requirement for selected products of tomato.
To work out cost and returns of selected tomato products.
To estimate break-even point for selected products of tomato.

To estimate value addition over the raw material in percentage.

To study marketing of selected tomato products.

To identify constraints in production and marketing of selected tomato products.

Methodology**Area of Study**

The present study was conducted at Nagpur Orange Growers Association (NOGA), Hingna dist. Nagpur.

Period of Study

The data was collected for FY 2023-2024 i.e., from April 2023 to March 2024.

Source of Data

Primary data was collected by pretested schedule from concern person, officials of selected firm by personal interview method regarding the production and marketing of tomato products.

Analytical Tools**Cost and Returns of Tomato Processing:**

The collected data related to required cost and returns from Tomato products were analyzed, tabulated on the following different aspects viz.

Fixed Cost:

The fixed cost includes the data regarding the cost of machinery, building, land, furniture, wages of payment employed labor, salary of staff, electricity charges, insurance premium and taxes. This information was collected from Nagpur Orange Growers Association (NOGA), Hingna dist. Nagpur.

Variable Cost:

The variable cost consists of expenditure on purchase of raw material, wages of casual labor, oil and lubricants, repair and maintenance of machinery, electricity and stationary charges, etc.

Total Cost:

Total cost was comprised of the total fixed cost and total variable cost and will be calculated by adding all these costs together.

Total cost = Fixed cost + Variable cost

Gross Returns:

The gross returns for processing of Tomato Products were calculated by adding together value of main product received after processing of 1. Tomato products. The gross returns defined as the total rate of return on an investment before the deduction of any expenses.

Gross returns = Quantity of product X Price per unit

Net Returns:

1.1.1.

The net returns refer to returns after deducting all expenses from the gross return generated by the investment.

Net returns = Gross returns – Total cost

B:C ratio:

The benefit cost ratio compares the present value of all benefits with that of the cost and investment of the project.

B:C ratio = Gross returns / Total cost

Breakeven Point Analysis:

The point at which the two curves i.e. total cost curve and total revenue curve intersect is called as breakeven point, which indicates the level of production at which neither losses money nor makes profit.

Computation in physical quantity,

$$BEP = F / (P - V)$$

Computation in monetary value,

$$BEP = F / [1 - (V/P)]$$

Where,

F = Annual fixed cost in Rs.

P = Selling price per unit in Rs.

V = Variable cost per unit in Rs.

Margin of safety:

The margin of safety (MOS) is the difference between your gross revenue and your break-even point.

Margin of Safety (in physical units) = Total output – output at BEP

Margin of Safety (in monetary value) = Total revenue – Revenue at BEP

Percentage of margin of safety = BEP / Volume of total output X 100

Marketing Cost:

The total cost incurred by the producer involved in packaging, transportation, sell and purchase of silkworms till it reaches to farmers.

Constraints faced by Producer:

The different constraints in production and marketing of Tomato products were identified by personal interview method.

Results and Discussion**Capital Requirement of Selected NOGA Processing Unit**

To fulfil the first objectives of the study in respect of organizational study of the Processing unit, the results has been obtained on capital investment, summary of capacity utilization are given as under.

Total Quantity Processed of Tomato Per Year at NOGA

Table 1. Total Quantity Processed of Tomato Per Year at NOGA

Sr. No.	Products	No. of days running	Raw Material (Kg)	Actual Processing Quantity (kg)	Percent share (%)
1	Tomato Ketchup	78	9740.64	34788	50.32
2	Tomato Sauce	55	6868.40	24530	35.48
3	Tomato Puree	22	2747.36	9812	14.19
	Total	155	19356.40	69130	100.00

Table 1 summarized the production performance of three tomato-based products—Tomato Ketchup, Tomato Sauce, and Tomato Puree—over 155 production days. Tomato Ketchup was produced for 78 days, using 9,740.64 kg of raw tomatoes to yield 34,788 kg of product, accounting for 50.32 per cent of total output. Tomato Sauce was produced for 55 days, consuming 6,868.40 kg of raw materials to produce 24,530 kg, representing 35.48 per cent of total output. Lastly, Tomato Puree was produced over 22 days, using 2,747.36 kg of raw materials to generate 9,812 kg, contributing 14.19 per cent. In total, 19,356.40 kg of raw tomatoes were processed, yielding 69,130 kg of finished products, with Tomato Ketchup being the dominant product in both raw material consumption and output.

Capital investment of the Selected Processing unit

Capital investment is the acquisition of physical assets by a company or a unit for use in furthering its long-term business goals and objectives.

Table 2. Capital investment of the Selected Processing unit

S.N.	Particulars	Amount (Rs in Lakhs)	Percent share (%)
1	Machinery	72.66	32.26
2	Building and other structure	110.58	49.10
3	Investment on land	8.7	3.86
4	Furniture and fixtures	0.62	0.28
5	Computer	0.75	0.33

6	Fan	0.15	0.07
7	Ac	0.31	0.14
8	Printer	0.24	0.11
9	Permanent staff	31.20	13.85
	Total	225.21	100.00

The table 2. Indicated the total, the investment amounted to Rs 225.21 lakhs, distributed across these categories detailed breakdown of the investment allocation across various components, The largest portion of the investment, 49.10 per cent, had been allocated to Building and other structures, amounted to Rs 110.58 lakhs. Machinery comes next, with an investment of Rs 72.66 lakhs, made up 32.26 per cent of the total. Permanent staff expenses represent a notable 13.85 per cent of the overall investment, at Rs 31.20 lakhs. Smaller allocations include Investment on land (Rs 8.70 lakhs, 3.86 per cent), Furniture and fixtures (Rs 0.62 lakhs, 0.28 per cent), Computers (Rs 0.75 lakhs, 0.33 per cent), Fans (Rs 0.15 lakhs, 0.07 per cent), AC (Rs 0.31 lakhs, 0.14 per cent), and Printers (Rs 0.24 lakhs, 0.11 per cent).

2. Cost and returns of selected unit

The study in respect of organizational study the result has been obtained on cost required, returns obtained from the unit given as under.

Fixed Cost

The fixed cost included the data regarding the cost of machinery, building, land, furniture, wages of payment employed labour, salary of staff, electricity charges, insurance premium and taxes. These are collected from NOGA, Hingna, Nagpur.

Table 3. Fixed cost of selected Processing of Tomato

S.N.	Particulars	Value Rs. in Lakhs	Percent share (%)
1	Machineries (@10% depreciation)	2.04	3.82
2	Building (@5% depreciation)	3.28	6.13
3	Furniture (@10% depreciation)	0.03	0.07
4	Computer	0.007	0.01
5	Fan	0.006	0.01
6	Ac	0.003	0.01
7	Printer	0.008	0.15
8	Taxes and insurance	12.00	22.42
9	Permanent employees		
	Manager	18.00	33.63
	Accountant	7.20	13.45
	Clerk	6.00	11.21
10	Interest on fixed capital @10%	4.86	9.09
	Total fixed cost	53.52	100.00

The table 3 presented a breakdown of fixed costs in a project, totaling Rs 53.52 lakhs. The largest expense, 33.63 per cent, was for the Manager's salary (Rs 18.00 lakhs), followed by Taxes and Insurance at 22.42 per cent (Rs 12.00 lakhs). Salaries for the Accountant and Clerk accounted for 13.45 per cent and 11.21 per cent, respectively. Depreciation costs included Rs 3.28 lakhs (6.13 per cent) for buildings and Rs 2.04 lakhs (3.82 per cent) for machinery. Minor assets, such as furniture and electronics, collectively accounted for less than 1 per cent, while interest on fixed capital (10 per cent) added Rs 4.86 lakhs, representing 9.09 per cent of the total. Most costs had focused on salaries, taxes, and interest.

Table 4. Product wise Fixed Cost at NOGA for year 2023-24

(Rs. In Lakh)

S.N.	Products	Output ratio for apportion	Fixed Cost
1	Tomato Ketchup	0.50	26.76
2	Tomato Sauce	0.36	19.11
3	Tomato Puree	0.14	7.64
	Total	1.00	53.52

Table 4 presented a breakdown of the fixed costs allocated to each tomato-based product for the fiscal year 2023-24, totaling Rs 53.52 lakhs. Costs were distributed based on output ratios, with Tomato Ketchup receiving the largest allocation of Rs 26.76 lakhs (50 per cent of output), followed by Tomato Sauce at Rs 19.11 lakhs (36 per cent of output), and Tomato Puree at Rs 7.64 lakhs (14 per cent of output). This distribution highlighted the significant contribution of Tomato Ketchup to overall production, emphasizing its predominant role among the three products.

Packaging of selected processing of Tomato

Packaging is a crucial aspect of processing and distribution of tomato products proper packaging ensures that tomatoes and their derivatives maintain, quality, safety, and marketability.

Packaging of Tomato Ketchup at NOGA

Table 5. Packaging of Tomato Ketchup at NOGA

S.N.	Packaging Material	Packaging Size	Quantity (kg)	No. of packing	Per Unit Cost (Rs.)	Total Cost (Rs.)	Percent share (%)
a.	Materials						
1	Glass bottle	1kg	10,780	10,780	5.00	53900	10.12
2	Glass bottle	200g	6,250	25,000	4.20	105000	19.71
3	Glass bottle	500g	7,500	15,000	4.50	67500	12.67
		Sub total	24,530	50,780	13.70	226400	42.50
b.	Labelling						
		12*4inch (L*W)	10,780	10,780	0.50	5390	1.01
		5*2inch(L*W)	25,000	25,000	0.20	5000	0.94
		5*2inch(L*W)	15,000	15,000	0.20	3000	0.56
		Sub total	50,780	50,780	0.90	13390	2.51
c.	Corrugated box & BOPP tape						
1	1kg(@12Bottles/box)	23.4*10.2*14.5 inch(L*W*H)	898	898	22.00	19756	3.71
2	200g(@12Bottles/box)	13*9*4inch (L*W*H)	2,083	2,083	10.00	20830	3.91
3	500g(@12Bottles/box)	13*9*4inch (L*W*H)	1,250	1,250	10.00	12500	2.35
		Sub total	2,981	2,981	42.00	53086	9.97
		Total	1,54,851	2,07,351	71.20	532666	100.00

The total packaging cost amounted to ₹7,03,504, with the majority of the expenses came from packaging materials like glass bottles, pouches, and sachets, which contribute Rs. 3,14,869.5, accounted for 44.76 per cent of the total cost. Labeling, included various sizes of labels, adds Rs. 12,462.5, represented 1.77 per cent. Corrugated boxes and BOPP tape, used for packing the bottles, contribute Rs. 48,840, or 6.94 per cent of the overall cost. Thus, the bulk of the expenses was driven by the materials used in packaging, made up nearly half of the total expenditure.

Packaging of Tomato Sauce at NOGA

NOGA (Nagpur Orange Growers Association) is known for producing a variety of processed products, including Tomato sauce. Here's an overview of how tomato Sauce is packaged at NOGA, focusing on materials, methods, design, and considerations.

Table 6. Packaging of Tomato Sauce at NOGA

The total packaging cost was Rs. 5,32,666, with packaging materials accounted for the largest share. Glass bottles, in sizes of 1kg, 200g, and 500g,

S.N.	Packaging Material	Packaging Size	Quantity (kg)	No. of packing	Per Unit Cost (Rs.)	Total Cost (Rs.)	Percent share (%)
a.	Materials						
1	Glass bottle	1kg	12,361	12,361	5.00	62,820	8.93
2	Glass bottle	200g	6,282	31,410	4.20	13,19,22	18.75
3	Pouch	950g	9,946.25	10,470	2.50	26,175	3.72
4	Pouch	450g	1,487.25	3,305	1.50	4,957.5	0.70
5	Sachet	15g	3,141	2,09,400	0.30	62,820	8.93
6	Sachet	12g	1,570.5	13,0875	0.20	26,175	3.72
		Sub total	34,788	39,7821	13.70	31,4869.5	44.76
b.	Labelling						
		12*4inch (L*W)	12,361	12,361	0.50	6,180.5	0.88
		5*2inch(L*W)	31,410	31,410	0.20	6,282	0.89
		Sub total	43,771	43,771	0.70	12,462.5	1.77
c.	Corrugated box & BOPP tape						
1	1kg(@12Bottles/box)	23.4*10.2*14.5 inch(L*W*H)	1,030	1,030	22.00	22,660	3.22
2	200g(@12Bottles/box)	13*9*4 inch (L*W*H)	2,618	2,618	10.00	26,180	3.72
		Sub total	3,648	3,648	32.00	48,840	6.94
		Total	1,60,766	8,86,832	60.80	7,03,504	100.00

cost Rs. 2,26,400, made up 42.50 per cent of the total. Labeling costs for different bottle sizes amounted Rs. 13,390, contributed 2.51 per cent. Corrugated boxes and BOPP tape, used for packing the bottles, add Rs. 53,086, which was 9.97 per cent of the total cost. Overall, the materials made up the bulk of the expenses, while labeling and packaging boxes/tape made smaller contributions, total 100 per cent of the packaging costs.

Packaging of Tomato Puree at NOGA

NOGA (Nagpur Orange Growers Association) is known for producing a variety of processed products, including Tomato Puree. Here's an overview of how tomato puree is packaged at NOGA, focusing on materials, methods, design, and considerations.

Table 7. Packaging of Tomato Puree at NOGA

S. N.	Packaging Material	Packaging Size	Quantity (kg)	No. of packing	Per Unit Cost (Rs.)	Total Cost (Rs.)	Percent share (%)
a	Material						
1	Tin can	850g	9,812.00	11,564.00	9.00	1,04,076	76.04
		Sub total	9,812.00	11,564.00	9.00	1,04,076	76.04
b	Labelling						
		5.75"*3.76(L*W)	11,564	11,564	0.50	5,782	4.22
		Sub total	11,564	11,564	0.50	5,782	4.22
c	Corrugated box & BOPP tape						
1	850g(@12Cans/box)	23.4*10.2*14.5 inch(L*W*H)	9,65	965	22.00	21,230	15.51
		Sub total	9,65	965	22.00	21,230	15.51
		Total	32,940.00	35,657.00	32.00	1,36,870	176.04

The above table indicated the total packaging expenditure amounted to Rs. 1,36,870 were organized into three main categories: Material, Labeling, and Corrugated Box & BOPP Tape. The Material section revealed that the tin can, sized at 850 grams, was the most significant expense, amounted to Rs. 1,04,076 and represented 76.04 per cent of the total packaging cost. This highlighted the critical role that the tin can plays in the overall budget. In the Labeling category, labels measured 5.75 inches by 3.76 inches contribute a total of Rs. 5,782, which constitutes 4.22 per cent of the overall expenditure. Although its share was relatively small, effective labeling was essential for product identification and marketing. The Corrugated Box & BOPP Tape section showed that the packaging for the cans-contained 12 cans per box-costs Rs. 21,230, accounted for 15.51 per cent of the total packaging expenses.

Variable Cost of Selected Processing of Tomato

The variable cost consists of expenditure on purchase of raw material, wages of casual labor, repair and maintenance of machinery, energy charges, postage, and stationery etc.

Variable cost of Tomato Ketchup at NOGA**Table 8. Variable cost of Tomato Ketchup at NOGA**

(Per season)					
S. N.	Particulars	Quantity	Per Unit Cost (Rs.)	Total Cost (Rs.)	Percent Share (%)
1	Raw Materials				
	a. Tomato Paste (Kg)	9,741.26	60.00	5,88,000	30.49
	b. Sugar (Kg)	10,436.40	32.00	3,33,965	14.66
	c. Salt (Kg)	869.70	8.00	6,958	0.31
	d. Spices (Kg)	8.697	1200.00	10,436	0.46
	e. Preservatives (Kg)	34.79	190.00	6610.1	0.29
	f. Acetic acid (kg)	34.79	70.00	2435.3	0.11
	g. Xanthan (Kg)	86.97	700.00	60,879	2.67
	h. Sterilize RO water (L)	13,567.32	5.00	67,837	2.98
2	Casual labour charges				
	a. Skilled Labour (@2labour/day)	156.00	320.00	50000	2.20
	b. Unskilled Labour (@13 labour/day)	1,014.00	275.00	279500	12.27
3	Repair and Maintenance (Rs.)			60,000	2.63
4	Electric, water, testing analysis charges (Rs.)			90,000	3.95
5	Postage, stationary and telephone charges (Rs.)			30,000	1.32
6	Packaging Material				
		160766	60.80	7,03,504	30.72
	Total			22,90,124	100.00
	Variable Cost per Kg	Output=34788		65.83	

The total production cost was Rs. 22,90,124, with raw materials and packaging largest contributors. Raw materials, included tomato paste, sugar, salt, spices, preservatives, acetic acid, xanthan gum, and sterilized RO water, made up Rs. 10,70,120.4, accounted for 46.97 per cent of the total cost, with tomato paste alone contributed 30.49 per cent. Labor charges, both skilled and unskilled, add Rs. 3,29,500 (14.47 per cent). Other expenses included repair and maintenance at Rs. 60,000 (2.63 per cent), electricity, water, and testing charges at Rs. 90,000 (3.95 per cent), and postage, stationery, and telephone charges at Rs. 30,000 (1.32 per cent). Packaging materials, cost Rs. 7,03,504, represented 30.72 per cent of the total expenditure. The variable cost per kg of output is Rs. 65.83.

Variable cost of Tomato Sauce at NOGA**Table 9. Variable cost of Tomato Sauce at NOGA**

(Per season)					
S. N.	Particulars	Quantity	Per Unit cost (Rs)	Total Cost (Rs.)	Percent Share (%)
1	Raw Materials				
	a. Tomato Paste (Kg)	6,860.40	60.00	4,11,624	26.08
	b. Sugar (Kg)	7,359	32.00	2,35,488	14.92
	c. Salt (kg)	613.25	8.00	4,906	0.31
	d. Spices (kg)	6.1325	1200.00	7,359	0.47
	e. Preservatives (kg)	24.53	190.00	4,661	0.30
	f. Acetic acid (Kg)	24.53	70.00	1,717	0.11
	g. Sterilize RO water (L)	9,573.70	5.00	47,869	3.03
2	Casual labour charges				
	a. Skilled Labour (@2labour/day)	110.00	320.00	35,200	2.23
	b. Unskilled Labour (@12labour/day)	660.00	275.00	1,81,500	11.50
3	Repair and maintenance (Rs.)			42,857	2.72
4	Energy charges, water, testing analysis charges (Rs.)			64,286	4.07
5	Postage, stationary and telephone charges (Rs.)			21,429	1.36
6	Packaging Material				
		1,54,851	71.20	532666	33.47
	Total			15,91,561	100.00
	Variable Cost per Kg	Output= 24530		64.88	

The total production cost was Rs. 15,91,561, with the largest portion allocated to raw materials and packaging. Raw materials, included tomato paste, sugar, salt, spices, preservatives, acetic acid, and sterilized RO water, accounted for Rs. 7,13,624, which was 44.22 per cent of the total cost, with tomato paste the highest contributor at 26.08per cent. Labor charges, both skilled and unskilled, total Rs. 2,16,700, made up 13.73 per cent. Additional costs included repair and maintenance at Rs. 42,857 (2.72 per cent), energy and water charges at Rs. 64,286 (4.07 per cent), and postage and stationary expenses at Rs. 21,429 (1.36per cent). Packaging materials cost Rs. 5,32,666, contributed 33.47per cent to the overall cost. The variable cost per kg of output was Rs. 64.88.

Variable cost of Tomato Puree at NOGA**Table 10. Variable cost of Tomato Puree at NOGA**

(Per season)					
S. N.	Particulars	Quantity	Per Unit cost (Rs)	Total Cost (Rs.)	Percent Share (%)
1	Raw Materials				
	a. Tomato Paste (Kg)	2747.36	60.00	1,64,842	39.99
	b. Preservatives (g)	9.812	190.00	1864.28	0.45
	c. Acetic acid	9.812	70.00	686.84	0.17
	d. Sterilize RO water	3838.68	5.00	19193.4	4.66
2	Casual labour charges				
	a. skilled Labour (@1labour/day)	22.00	320.00	7040	1.71
	b. unskilled Labour (@5labour/day)	110.00	275.00	30,250	7.34
3	Repair and maintenance (Rs.)			17,143	4.16

4	Energy charges, water, testing analysis charge (Rs.)			25,714	6.24
5	Postage, stationary and telephone charges (Rs.)			8,571	2.08
6	Packaging Material				
		32,940.00	32.00	136870	33.21
	Total			4,12,174	100.00
	Variable Cost per Kg	Output=9812		42.01	

The table 10 indicated that the production process for 9,812 kg of tomato puree was heavily driven by raw material costs, with tomato paste was the largest contributor, accounted for Rs. 1,64,842 or 39.99 per cent of the total cost. Other raw materials, such as preservatives, acetic acid, and sterilized RO water, together made up smaller portions, with costs of Rs. 1,864.28 (0.45 per cent), Rs. 686.84 (0.17 per cent), and Rs. 19,193.40 (4.66 per cent) respectively. Labor costs were divided between skilled labor (Rs. 7,040 or 1.71 per cent) and unskilled labor (Rs. 30,250 or 7.34 per cent). Operational expenses such as repair and maintenance (Rs. 17,143 or 4.16 per cent), energy charges, water, and testing analyzed (Rs. 25,714 or 6.24 per cent), and postage, stationary, and telephone charges (Rs. 8,571 or 2.08 per cent) add to the overall costs. Additionally, packaging materials form a significant portion, cost Rs. 1,36,870 or 33.21 per cent of the total. In total, the production cost amounted to Rs. 4,12,174, with a variable cost of Rs. 42.01 per kg of output.

Marketing Cost of Selected Processing of Tomato

The total cost incurred by the producer and various intermediaries involved in sell and purchase of Tomato by- products till it reaches to consumer.

Table 11. Marketing Cost of Selected Processing of Tomato

(Per season)

S. N.	Particulars	Tomato Processed Products					
		Tomato Ketchup		Tomato Sauce		Tomato Puree	
		Cost (Rs.)	Percent share (%)	Cost (Rs.)	Percent share (%)	Cost (Rs.)	Percent share (%)
1	Transportation cost	140000	32.18	100000	30.77	40000	20.00
2	Advertisement cost	50000	11.49	50000	15.38	10000	5.00
3	Commission charges	245000	56.32	175000	53.85	150000	75.00
	Total	435000	100.00	325000	100.00	200000	100.00
4	Total output processed (Kg)	34788		24530		9812	
5	Marketing cost/ Kg	12.50		13.25		20.38	

The total marketing costs for tomato processed products - ketchup, sauce, and puree-were primarily driven by transportation, advertisement, and commission charges. For tomato ketchup, the total marketing cost was Rs. 4,35,000, with transportation accounted for 32.18 per cent, advertisement for 11.49 per cent, and commission charges was the largest at 56.32 per cent. Tomato sauce had a total cost of Rs. 3,25,000, where transportation made up 30.77 per cent, advertisement 15.38 per cent, and commission 53.85 per cent. Tomato puree had the lowest total marketing cost of Rs. 2,00,000, with transportation at 20 per cent, advertisement at 5 per cent, and commission charges dominated at 75 per cent. The cost per kilogram was Rs. 12.50 for ketchup, Rs. 13.25 for sauce, and Rs. 20.38 for puree, made puree the most expensive in terms of marketing cost per kg.

Total Cost of Selected Processing of Tomato

Table 12. Total Cost of Selected Processing of Tomato

(Per season)

S. N.	Particulars	Tomato Processed Products					
		Tomato Ketchup		Tomato Sauce		Tomato Puree	
		Cost (Rs.)	Percent share (%)	Cost (Rs.)	Percent share (%)	Cost (Rs.)	Percent share (%)
1	Fixed cost (Rs in Lakhs)	26.76	49.55	19.11	49.93	7.64	55.52
2	Variable cost (Rs in Lakhs)	22.90	42.40	15.91	41.57	4.12	29.94
3	Marketing cost (Rs in Lakhs)	4.35	8.05	3.25	8.49	2.00	14.53
	Total cost (Rs in Lakhs)	54.01	100.00	38.27	100.00	13.76	100.00
	Total cost /kg	155.25		156.01		140.24	

Table 12 provided a cost analysis of three tomato-based processed products: Tomato Ketchup, Tomato Sauce, and Tomato Puree. Tomato Ketchup had a total cost of Rs. 54.01 lakhs, with fixed costs of Rs. 26.76 lakhs (49.55 per cent), variable costs of Rs. 22.90 lakhs (42.40 per cent), and marketing expenses of Rs. 4.35 lakhs (8.05 per cent). Tomato Sauce's total cost was Rs. 38.27 lakhs, including fixed costs of Rs. 19.11 lakhs (49.93 per cent), variable costs of Rs. 15.91 lakhs (41.57 per cent), and marketing expenses of Rs. 3.25 lakhs (8.49 per cent). Tomato Puree had a total cost of Rs. 13.76 lakhs, with fixed costs of Rs. 7.64 lakhs (55.52 per cent), variable costs of Rs. 4.12 lakhs (29.94 per cent), and marketing costs of Rs. 2.00 lakhs (14.53 per cent).

Gross Return of NOGA Products in 2023-24

The gross returns for processing of Tomato Ketchup were calculated by adding together value of main product received after processing of 1 kg Tomato Ketchup. The gross returns defined as the total rate of return on an investment before the deduction of any expenses.

Table 13. Gross Return of NOGA Products in 2023-24

(Per season)

S.N.	Products	Production (kg)	Rate	Total Return (Rs. In Lakhs)	Percent share (%)
1	Tomato Ketchup	34788	225	78.27	52.82
2	Tomato Sauce	24530	225	55.19	37.25
3	Tomato Puree	9812	150	14.72	9.93
	Total			148.18	100.00

The table 13 provided an overview of the gross returns for NOGA products in the year 2023-24, detailed the production volumes, selling rates, total returns, and percentage shares for each product. Tomato Ketchup led with a production of 34,788 kg, generated a total return of Rs. 78.27 lakhs, which represented 52.82 per cent of the total returns. Followed this, Tomato Sauce produced 24,530 kg, yield a total return of Rs. 55.19 lakhs, accounted for 37.25 per cent of the overall returns. Tomato Puree, with a production of 9,812 kg, generated the least total return of Rs. 14.72 lakhs, contributed 9.93 per cent to the total. In summary, the total gross return for all NOGA products amounted to Rs. 148.18 lakhs, with Tomato Ketchup was the most significant contributor, underscored its prominence and profitability within the product lineup.

Economics of Processing of NOGA Products

The details of economics of processing of tomato ketchup presented in Table no. 14.

Table 14. Economics of Processing of NOGA Products

S.N.	Particulars	Tomato Processed Products		
		Tomato Ketchup	Tomato Sauce	Tomato Puree
1	Production in Kg	34788	24530	9812
2	Fixed Cost (Rs. in Lakhs)	26.76	19.11	7.64
3	Variable Cost (Rs. in Lakhs)	22.90	15.92	4.12
4	Variable Cost per Kg	65.83	64.88	42.01
5	Marketing Cost (Rs. in Lakhs)	4.35	3.25	2.00
6	Total Cost (Rs. in Lakhs)	54.01	38.28	13.76
7	Gross Returns (Rs. in Lakhs)	78.27	55.19	14.72
8	Price per Kg	225	225	150
9	Net Profit (Rs. in Lakhs)	24.26	16.92	0.96
10	Input: output ratio (1: __)	1.45	1.44	1.07

Table 14 provided a financial overview of three processed tomato products: Tomato Ketchup, Tomato Sauce, and Tomato Puree. Production quantities were 34,788 kg for Ketchup, 24,530 kg for Sauce, and 9,812 kg for Puree. Fixed costs were Rs. 26.76 lakhs for Ketchup, Rs. 19.11 lakhs for Sauce, and Rs. 7.64 lakhs for Puree, with variable costs of Rs. 22.90 lakhs, Rs. 15.92 lakhs, and Rs. 4.12 lakhs, respectively. Marketing costs totaled Rs. 4.35 lakhs for Ketchup, Rs. 3.25 lakhs for Sauce, and Rs. 2.00 lakhs for Puree. Total costs reached Rs. 54.01 lakhs for Ketchup, Rs. 38.28 lakhs for Sauce, and Rs. 13.76 lakhs for Puree. Gross returns were Rs. 78.27 lakhs for Ketchup, Rs. 55.19 lakhs for Sauce, and Rs. 14.72 lakhs for Puree, resulting in net profits of Rs. 24.26 lakhs for Ketchup, Rs. 16.92 lakhs for Sauce, and Rs. 0.96 lakhs for Puree. Input-output ratios were 1.45 for Ketchup, 1.44 for Sauce, and 1.07 for Puree.

Breakeven point Analysis of Selected NOGA Products

The break-even point shows the optimum quantity of raw material to be processed to justify purchase of particular machinery. One of the objectives of particular study was estimate break-even point for the tomato processing unit result in the behalf is presented as follows:

Table 15. Breakeven point Analysis of Selected NOGA Products

S.N.	Particulars	Tomato Processed Products			Total
		Tomato Ketchup	Tomato Sauce	Tomato Puree	
1	Production in Kg	34788	24530	9812	69130
2	Fixed Cost (Rs. in Lakhs)	26.76	19.11	7.64	53.52
3	Variable Cost (Rs. in Lakhs)	22.90	15.92	4.12	42.94
4	Variable Cost per Kg	65.83	64.88	42.01	57.57
5	Price per Kg	225	225	150	200
6	Break Even Point (Kg) (physical quantity)	15750	12497	6885	37013
7	Break Even Point (Rs) (Monetary value)	2675996	1910997	763996	5351996
8	Margin of Safety(Physical Quantity) Kg	19250	12503	3115	32987
9	Margin of safety (Monetary Value) Rs	5187970	3705705	732320	9625911
10	Percentage of Margin of Safety	45.00	49.99	68.85	52.88

Table 15 provided a concise financial analysis of three processed tomato products: Tomato Ketchup, Tomato Sauce, and Tomato Puree. It detailed production quantities, with a total of 69,130 kg, led by Ketchup at 34,788 kg. The total fixed costs amounted to Rs. 53.52 lakhs, while total variable costs reached Rs. 42.94 lakhs. The average selling price per kilogram was Rs. 200, with both Ketchup and Sauce priced at Rs. 225 each. The overall break-even point was calculated at 37,013 kg, corresponding to a monetary value of Rs. 5,351,996. Additionally, the margin of safety totaled 32,987

kg, indicating a healthy buffer against potential losses, with an overall margin of safety percentage of 52.88%. This analysis effectively highlighted the financial performance and risk management strategies associated with these processed tomato products.

Value addition over raw material in percent

Value addition is a fundamental concept in economics, business, and manufacturing, as it reflects how inputs are transformed to produce greater output and value in the marketplace.

Table 16. Value addition over raw material in percent

(Rs/Kg)

S.N.	Particulars	Tomato Processed Products		
		Tomato Ketchup	Tomato Sauce	Tomato Puree
1	Purchased price of raw material (Tomato Paste)	28.75	28.75	16.99
2	Processing cost of raw material (Rs)	155.25	156.01	140.24
3	Price of Processed Products (Rs)	225	225	150
4	Increased in the value of processed product (Rs)	196.25	196.25	133.01
5	Percent increase in the value of Processed product over raw material (%)	682.60	682.61	782.87

The table 16 analyzed the value addition in processed tomato products: Tomato Ketchup, Tomato Sauce, and Tomato Puree. The purchased price of raw material (Tomato Paste) was Rs. 28.75 for Ketchup and Sauce, while Puree costs Rs. 16.99. Processing costs were Rs. 155.25 for Ketchup, Rs. 156.01 for Sauce, and Rs. 140.24 for Puree. The selling prices were Rs. 225 for Ketchup and Sauce, and Rs. 150 for Puree, led to an increase in value of Rs. 196.25 for Ketchup and Sauce, and Rs. 133.01 for Puree. The percentage increase in value over the raw material cost was about 682.61 per cent for Ketchup and Sauce, and 782.87 per cent for Puree, highlighted the significant financial benefits of processing.

Constraints in production and marketing of selected tomato products

Producer faces various constraints when it comes to production and marketing. These constraints can impact the efficiency and success of their operations. Here are some main constraints are as follow:

Table 17. Constraints in production and marketing of selected tomato products

Sr. No.	Particulars	Rank
I	Production Constraints	
1	Maintain strictly labor health and safety standards	I
2	Perishable products have a limited shelf life	II
3	Cost of raw materials fluctuation	III
II	Marketing Constraints	
1	No competitive brand in market	I
2	Less number of outlets	II
3	Low brand awareness	III

The table 17 ranks the production and marketing constraints faced by a processed tomato products company. In production, the top constraint is maintaining strict labor health and safety standards, followed by the limited shelf life of perishable products and fluctuations in raw material costs. In marketing, the absence of competitive brands is the highest-ranked constraint, indicated a strong market opportunity but a need for brand establishment. This is followed by a limited number of retail outlets and low brand awareness, which hinder market reach and consumer access.

Conclusions

6. Tomato Ketchup was the top product with 34,788 kg produced, contributing 50.32 per cent of total output, followed by Tomato Sauce at 24,530 kg and Tomato Puree at 9,812 kg. Total raw material usage was 19,356.40 kg, resulting in a processed output of 69,130 kg.

49.10 per cent of the total investment of Rs. 110.58 lakh was allocated to buildings and structures, with machinery receiving Rs. 72.66 lakh. Land investment was Rs. 8.7 lakh, and total capital investment amounted to Rs. 225.21 lakh.

Total fixed costs were Rs. 53.52 lakh, with depreciation on machinery and buildings contributing nearly 10 per cent. Major costs included taxes, insurance, and salaries, which represented 22.42 per cent and 33.63 per cent, respectively.

Fixed costs were highest for Tomato Ketchup at Rs. 26.76 lakh, followed by Sauce at Rs. 19.11 lakh and Puree at Rs. 7.64 lakh. Variable costs per kg were Rs. 65.83 for Ketchup, Rs. 64.88 for Sauce, and Rs. 42.01 for Puree, total Rs. 42.94 lakh.

Tomato Ketchup had the highest variable cost per kg at Rs. 65.83, with an average of Rs. 57.57 across all products. Tomato Puree had the highest proportion of fixed costs at 55.52 per cent.

Labor costs made up 12-13 per cent of variable costs in Ketchup and Sauce production, while maintenance and overhead costs accounted for 6-8 per cent.

Marketing costs per kg were highest for Tomato Puree at Rs. 20.38, followed by Sauce at Rs. 13.25 and Ketchup at Rs. 12.50. Commissions were the largest marketing expense, particularly for Puree.

The break-even point for Ketchup was 15,750 kg, while Puree had the lowest at 6,885 kg. The margin of safety was highest for Puree at 68.85 per cent.

Gross returns total Rs. 148.18 lakh, with Ketchup contributing 52.82 per cent, Sauce 37.25 per cent, and Puree 9.93 per cent. Ketchup and Sauce showed a value increase of 682.61 per cent, while Puree had a 782.87 per cent increase, indicating strong profitability.

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